

Менеджмент

UDC: 658:339.9:004

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20668122>

**Conceptual models and methodological tools for diagnosing organizational
social and communication support**

Blyznyuk Tetyana,

Doctor of Sciences (Economics), Professor,
Head of Creative Management and Design Department
Simon Kuznets Kharkiv National University of Economics
61165 Kharkiv, Nayki av., 9a
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8291-4150>

Wang Honghai

PhD student of Creative Management and Design Department
Simon Kuznets Kharkiv National University of Economics, Ukraine,
61165 Kharkiv, Nayki av., 9a
Associate Professor, Tourism College of Zhejiang, Hangzhou, China
<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-3147-6509>

Accepted: 20.05.2026 | Published: 28.05.2026

Abstract. The article presents the results of developing a conceptual model and methodological tools for diagnosing the social and communication support (SCS) of organizations under the conditions of digital transformation and martial law in Ukraine. The relevance of the study stems from the need for domestic enterprises to adapt to high uncertainty, structural changes in labor collectives (feminization, aging personnel,

shortage of male labor), and the growing role of communications as a strategic resource.

The empirical basis of the study is an expert sociological survey conducted in 2026 in 45 Ukrainian organizations of various fields of activity (production - 26.7%, services - 73.3%) and forms of ownership (state - 57.8%, private - 42.2%). A set of methods was used: questionnaires, technical audits, documentation analysis, and monitoring of communication metrics, which ensured data triangulation.

The study found significant gaps in the SCS systems of Ukrainian organizations. The most problematic was the cultural-value mechanism: only 26.7% of employees fully share the organization's values, and 22.2% perceive them as purely formal. A low level of systematic feedback was recorded (13.3% of organizations). It was found that 25% of manufacturing enterprises are at the low and transitional levels of VSC development, while none have reached a high level. In the service sector, 30.3% of organizations have a low level of VSC development, and only 6% have reached a high level. Based on the data obtained, a conceptual model of VSC was developed, which integrates four interrelated levels: institutional, technical, cultural-value, and behavioral-management. To quantitatively assess the level of VSC development, an integral indicator, IvSC, with differentiated weighting factors for the manufacturing and service sectors, was proposed. A methodological diagnostic toolkit has been developed, including questionnaires, technical audits, communication metrics, and analytical frameworks, that enables regular monitoring of the state of the VCS.

Differentiated practical recommendations have been formulated along three dimensions: by the type of VCS development (adaptive, with hidden potential, technologically dependent, with a critical gap), by the field of activity (production or services), and by the form of ownership (state or private). The implementation of the proposed recommendations will improve the effectiveness of social and communication support, increase staff involvement, and strengthen organizations' adaptability to changes in the external environment.

Keywords: social and communication support, diagnostics, monitoring, conceptual model, organizational communication, integral indicator, cultural and value mechanism, differentiated recommendations.

**Концептуальні моделі та методологічний інструментарій діагностики
організаційного соціально-комунікаційного забезпечення**

Близнюк Тетяна Павлівна,

д. е. н., професор, завідувач кафедри креативного менеджменту і дизайну,
Харківський національний економічний університет
імені Семена Кузнеця, М. Харків, пр. Науки 9а, 61165,
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8291-4150>

Ван Хунхай,

аспірант кафедри креативного менеджменту і дизайну
Харківський національний економічний університет імені Семена
Кузнеця, м. Харків, пр. Науки 9а, 61165
доцент, Коледж туризму Чжецзяня, Китай,
<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-3147-6509>

Анотація. У статті представлено результати розробки концептуальної моделі та методичного інструментарію для діагностики соціально-комунікаційного забезпечення (СКЗ) організацій в умовах цифрової трансформації та воєнного стану в Україні. Актуальність дослідження зумовлена необхідністю адаптації вітчизняних підприємств до високої невизначеності, структурних змін у трудових колективах (фемінізація, старіння персоналу, дефіцит чоловічої робочої сили) та зростання ролі комунікацій як стратегічного ресурсу.

Емпіричною основою дослідження є експертне соціологічне опитування, проведене у 2026 році в 45 українських організаціях різних сфер діяльності (виробництво – 26,7%, послуги – 73,3%) та форм власності (державна – 57,8%, приватна – 42,2%). Використовувався комплекс методів: анкетування, технічні аудити, аналіз документації, моніторинг комунікаційних метрик, що забезпечив триангуляцію даних.

Результати дослідження показали суттєві прогалини в системі СКЗ українських організацій. Найбільш проблематичним виявився культурно-ціннісний механізм: лише 26,7% співробітників повністю поділяють цінності організації, а 22,2% сприймають їх як суто формальні. Зафіксовано низький рівень систематичного зворотного зв'язку (13,3% організацій). Виявлено, що 25% виробничих підприємств перебувають на межі низького та перехідного рівнів розвитку СКЗ, водночас жодне з них не досягло високого рівня. У сфері послуг 30,3% організацій мають низький рівень розвитку СКЗ, і лише 6% досягли високого рівня.

На основі отриманих даних розроблено концептуальну модель СКЗ, яка інтегрує чотири взаємопов'язані рівні: інституційний, технічний, культурно-ціннісний та поведінково-управлінський. Для кількісної оцінки рівня розвитку СКЗ запропоновано інтегральний показник Іскз з диференційованими ваговими коефіцієнтами для виробничого сектору та сектору послуг. Розроблено методичний діагностичний інструментарій, який включає анкети, технічні аудити, комунікаційні метрики та аналітичні рамки й дає змогу регулярно контролювати стан СКЗ.

Сформульовано диференційовані практичні рекомендації за трьома вимірами: за типом розвитку СКЗ (адаптивний, з прихованим потенціалом, технологічно залежний, з критичним розривом), за сферою діяльності (виробництво або послуги) та за формою власності (державна чи приватна). Впровадження запропонованих рекомендацій сприятиме підвищенню ефективності соціальної та комунікаційної підтримки, зростанню залученості

персоналу та посиленню адаптивності організацій до змін у зовнішньому середовищі.

Ключові слова: соціально-комунікаційна підтримка, діагностика, моніторинг, концептуальна модель, організаційна комунікація, інтегральний показник, культурно-ціннісний механізм, диференційовані рекомендації.

The statement of the problem. In today's highly uncertain environment, caused by martial law, economic upheavals, and digital transformation, effective internal organizational communication is no longer an ancillary function but a strategic resource that ensures team survival and cohesion. Research shows significant changes in the structure of the workforce: due to military events, mobilization, and migration, the shortage of male labor has led to an increased role for women in ensuring the smooth operation of enterprises (75.6% of respondents were women).

Although most organizations recognize the importance of communication processes, they still face numerous problems: communication procedures are formalized but lack practical effectiveness; technologies are disconnected from cultural integration; systematic feedback mechanisms are lacking; and employees have a low level of identification with corporate values. Research shows that only 13.3% of organizations regularly assess communication effectiveness, and that only 13.3% implement systematic feedback mechanisms.

Therefore, there is an urgent need to develop a systematic approach to diagnosing, monitoring, and improving the organization's social and communication support, considering the specific needs of different industries and institutions.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The theoretical and methodological foundations of social and communicative support (SCS) have been studied by scientists both domestically and abroad. Among Ukrainian scientists, the studies of V. Rizun [8], I. Shpektorenko [9] and O. Kostyuk [2], who consider communication a systemic phenomenon and an integral function of management,

deserve attention. M. Vasylyk [11] emphasizes the universality of communication in the entire management system.

In the Western scientific community, the classical linear model (K. Shannon, V. Weaver [2]; D. Berlo [1]) was supplemented by interactive methods (K. Osgood, V. Schramm [7]), which transformed our understanding of communication from one-way behavior to a two-way dialogue, which is of crucial importance for our study.

Modern research focuses on internal communication (M. Welch, A. Verčič [2; 5]), the strategic role of communication (A. Zerfass, P. Argenti [9]) and cultural specificity, particularly in Asia (M. Lee, B. Kim [8]; Jang Jeni [4]), which influence the formation of loyalty and collectivist values.

Despite all the research, the problem of organizational social and communication support requires deepening and further development.

The purpose of the research. The purpose of this article is to develop and demonstrate a conceptual model and methodological tools for diagnosing organizational social and communication support, and to provide differentiated practical recommendations for increasing its effectiveness, taking into account the specifics of different industries and institutions.

Presentation of main research materials. Literature analysis shows that the classical linear communication model (Shannon-Weaver model) [2] and SMCR (Bello model) [6] can construct the technical layer of data transmission. Meanwhile, Bandura's social learning theory [7] explains how symbolic communication influences employee behavior, as reflected in our culture and values module. Considering the modern digital transformation [10], our model combines the technical infrastructure with the behavioral layer.

The empirical basis of this study is a sociological survey conducted by the authors in 2026. The expert group included managers and senior managers of commercial enterprises, representatives of small and medium-sized enterprises, as well as employees of organizations of various forms of ownership and sizes. The questionnaires were anonymous, 45 valid questionnaires were received.

The sample structure was characterized by the following: 75.6% were women and 24.4% were men; the largest number (44.4%) were aged 46 years and older; 84.4% of respondents had higher or postgraduate education. The employment structure was mainly professional (44.4%) and managerial (28.9%). The majority of the surveyed organizations provided services (73.3%) and were state-owned (57.8%).

It is proposed to view an organization's social and communication support (SCS) as a multi-level system that combines formal and informal mechanisms for information exchange, action coordination, and support for corporate culture. Based on the research by Kostyuk [9] (which identified four key subsystems: social, technological, informational, and managerial) and considering the modern requirements of digital transformation [8], the authors clarified and systematized the components of the SCS.

Table 1

Components of the social and communication support system of the organization

Subsystem	Main elements	Characteristics
Institutional	Communication strategy, management structure	Forms communication rules, roles and procedures
Information	Data, channels, information policy	Ensures accessibility, accuracy and relevance of information
Social	Qualifications, psychological qualities, interaction style	Affects cohesion, loyalty, adaptability
Technical	Communications, technical infrastructure	Determines the speed, accessibility and quality of information transfer

Source: developed by the author

As shown in Table 1, the proposed framework encompasses four interrelated levels. The institutional subsystem establishes the regulatory framework for communication; the information subsystem is responsible for content; the social subsystem accounts for human factors (emotions, style, skills); and the technological subsystem provides data transmission channels. This approach avoids reductionism and balances the «hard» (structure, rules) and «soft» (culture, values) components of trauma, which is crucial for the development of effective diagnostic methods.

This approach implements a four-level diagnostic framework: first, different mechanisms (institutions, technologies, cultural values, and behavioral management)

are assessed, and then the results are integrated into a weighted composite index I_{scs} , which allows positioning the organization based on supply chain maturity.

The flowchart in Fig. 1 illustrates the comprehensive diagnostic approach developed in this study. The diagram demonstrates the sequential movement from primary data collection to the integral indicator and its interpretation.

Analysis of the survey results shows that the most common types of social communication are official communication (29.9%) and personal communication (23.6%). The priority order of the principles for building the Social Communication System (SCS) is also determined: in the areas of general assessment and production, systematicity takes first place; while in services, the highest priority is given to ethical and responsible principles.

Source: developed by the author

Fig. 1. Logic of assessing the components of the organization's social and communication support system

Analyzing Table 2, we conclude that the most problematic area was the cultural and value mechanism: 31.1% of respondents noted the need for significant changes, and 60% for partial ones. Only in one organization was there no need to change institutional mechanisms.

A diagnostic study of the state of SCS in 45 organizations [10] across different industries and ownership structures revealed significant differences in maturity levels and structural imbalances among the system's components. In particular, the study found that a significant number of organizations had a strong technological foundation but weak cultural elements («potential»); others relied excessively on technology and did not have an appropriate institutional foundation («technologically dependent»); and still others lagged significantly behind in development along several dimensions («critical gap»). Only a few organizations (mostly concentrated in the service sector) reached a balanced «adaptive» level.

Table 2

Analysis of the need for changes in the components of the social and communication support system of organizations, depending on the field of activity

Scope of activity	Large extent	Some extent	Small extent	No require
Institutional mechanism				
Production	4	8	0	0
Services	6	19	7	1
Cultural and value mechanism				
Production	3	7	1	1
Services	11	20	2	0

Source: developed by the author

This diversity makes it impossible to apply a single approach to improving the effectiveness of SCS. Therefore, practical recommendations should not only be meaningful but also tailored to individual needs, fully considering the specific type of SPE development, industry affiliation (manufacturing or service), and ownership

structure (state or private). Such an approach can exert a targeted managerial influence and increase the likelihood of achieving the desired changes.

Table 3 summarizes the main characteristics of each SMC, identifies priority areas for development, and outlines specific management measures to improve the effectiveness of communication support.

The above data show that the most beneficial but least common type is the «adaptive» type, which only requires supportive measures. In contrast, the «potential» and «technology-dependent» types require targeted interventions in the cultural or institutional spheres, respectively. The type that requires the greatest investment in resources is the «critical gap» that can only be effectively addressed through a comprehensive transformation plan. Thus, the proposed typology allows organizations to select the most relevant strategies for improving information systems and to accurately allocate limited resources to specific «areas of urgent need» within each type, thereby avoiding resource dispersion.

Table 3

Recommended measures to improve the efficiency of the VMS depending on its type

Type of SCS	Key characteristics	Priority areas	Recommended measures
Adaptive	Balanced development of all components	Continuous improvement	In-depth analytics, innovation, knowledge sharing systems
Hidden potential	Strong technical base, weak cultural component	Development of organizational culture	Internal communications programs, alignment of values
Technologically dependent	Dominance of technical means, weak institutional and cultural components	Institutionalization	Formalization of procedures, systemic feedback
Critical gap	Low development of many components	Comprehensive transformation	Integrated program for improving the quality of life, leadership development

Source: developed by the author based on diagnostic data and a tested VCI maturity model

In addition to type, key contextual factors influencing recommendations include the industry and ownership structure. The analysis of secondary data reveals significant differences in priorities between manufacturing and service companies, as well as between public and private entities.

For manufacturing companies, priorities include:

strengthening formal communication channels (clear vertical communication, directives, and regulations);

improving interdepartmental coordination (establishing diagonal and horizontal connections);

strengthening the integration of digitalization into operational processes (MES, ERP, IIoT).

For service companies, key priorities include:

developing interpersonal communication (empathy training, active listening);

strengthening organizational culture and trust (co-creation of value, recognition programs);

implementing customer-centric communication strategies (customer feedback, communication mapping).

Differences in ownership structure are no less important. For national institutions, where research indicates the prevalence of formalism and outdated technological infrastructure, the following measures are recommended:

modernizing technological infrastructure (upgrading computers, networks, and software);

overcoming formalism in communication processes (moving from “reporting for the sake of reporting” to real key performance indicators);

«revitalizing» organizational culture (organizing internal events, improving informal communication, and encouraging employee initiative).

For private enterprises, which usually have a strong technological base but lack managerial capabilities, the following measures are recommended:

investing in managerial skills (leadership, communication skills, and conflict resolution training);

systematization of communication (ensuring compliance with rules and regulations without excessive bureaucracy);

promotion of successful practices (standardization of solutions that have proven effective in the department/region).

Thus, the proposed three-dimensional differentiation (type of SCS, business area, form of ownership) provides a reliable basis for developing targeted, realistic management solutions that fully account for the unique context of each organization. This increases the effectiveness of recommendations and reduces the risk of «standardization error».

Conclusion. This study demonstrates that organizational social and communication support is a complex system that integrates institutional, technological, cultural values, and behavioral management aspects. The proposed conceptual model can systematically diagnose and improve social and communication support systems, account for relationships among components, and ensure the integrity of managerial influence.

An empirical study of 45 Ukrainian organizations revealed significant shortcomings in their social and communication support systems. The cultural values mechanism was the most noticeable: only 26.7% of employees fully identified with their organization's values, while 22.2% considered these values a mere formality. In addition, the level of implementation of systematic feedback mechanisms was low - only 13.3% of organizations regularly assessed the effectiveness of communication, and the level of implementation of systematic feedback mechanisms was only 13.3%. This suggests that formalized communication procedures often lack practical effectiveness, and technological tools do not complement effective cultural integration.

To address these gaps, we have developed a methodological diagnostic toolkit comprising questionnaires, technology audits, communication indicators, and an analytical framework. This toolkit enables regular monitoring of the Service Value

Chain System (SVCS), tracking its dynamic changes over time and promptly identifying negative trends. The comprehensive indicator we propose, Iscs, is particularly important because it quantifies the overall level of SCS development and compares the situation across organizations or over time.

Based on the diagnostic results, we developed differentiated and practical recommendations that consider three key dimensions: the type of SCS development (adaptive, potentially growing, technology-dependent or with critical gaps), the business sector (production or service), and the form of ownership (public or private). This three-dimensional differentiation enables targeted management interventions, allowing organizations to accurately allocate limited resources among the most complex components of the SCS.

The implementation of these recommendations will help to increase the effectiveness of social and communication support, increase employee engagement and satisfaction (primarily by bridging the gap between established values and actual practice), and strengthen the organization's adaptability to changes in the external environment, which is especially important during periods of martial law and economic turmoil in Ukraine.

Future research directions include developing industry standards to support the value chain (SCS); adapting the proposed tools for different types of organizations; and conducting longitudinal studies to assess the dynamics of change following the implementation of the recommendations. Attention should be paid to the impact of digital transformation on communication processes and to adapting diagnostic methodologies to the current state of hybrid and remote work, as these models are becoming increasingly common in modern organizations.

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